

THE IDEAS OF HUMANISM IN ENGLISH LITERATURE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7655805>

Annotation. Before moving on to the paper's major issue, it is important to explain when humanism first appeared in English literature, who its forerunners were, and where English literature stood during the old, middle, and classical Renaissance periods. Invasion from abroad and internal conflict characterize the roughly 500–1100 AD period in British history. The Romans left the British Isles in 407 AD, and the fifth century saw the victories and gradual occupations of Germanic tribes, angels, Jutes, and Saxons who went from Scandinavia to Britain. This led to the blending of numerous ethnicities, the tongue, and cultures. The great king Alfred (871–900 AD) stopped the Vikings' advance (known as the Norman of Danes). Long before the language was put into writing, singing people like scop gleeman or bards would use it to make joy by singing about the day's battles or old sagas in the evening. Their songs and poems were inspired by their love of pastoral independence, their love of nature, their roles, their regard for womanhood, and their struggle for glory as a driving force in every noble life. The scop (singer) and gleeman (poet) were also affiliated with the court. English, which sprang from the languages of the Angles, Jutes, and Saxons, was mostly Germanic. As a result, Latin had a significant influence on the language.

Keywords: humanism, English literature, literary language, poetry, prose, social culture, famous humanists, human life.

Introduction. Vikings from Scandinavia later added numerous words to old English. Old English had become a well-established literary language by the end of the old English period, which was characterized by Norman conquests. Verification was first used in English literature, both in written and spoken form. War, conquering, and courage themes predominated Old English poetry. In the seventh and ninth centuries, respectively, prominent English poets of religion included Caedmon and Cynwulf. Before Beowulf was set in a Christian environment in the 8th century, it retained all the characteristics of the pagan past, including brief pagan poems that each praised a different heroic deed. The poem Beowulf, which has roughly 3182 words, is pagan in its depiction of untamed natural settings, ferocious weather, and a harsh climate, including

stormy seas, fatal fogs, hail, rain, and marshy regions. In the words of Calamines and Legouis,

“Beowulf is every part a hero: the ideal of an active force serving good and triumphing over evil...”

In the ninth century, old English prose began to emerge after poetry. Moreover, it occasionally contained aspects of poetry; it was influenced by Latin, the church language, and educated individuals. It had historical, theological, and factual context. One of the most important kings of the first millennium, King Alfred the Great (871–900 AD), translated many works from Latin, particularly in the fields of philosophy, history, and religion. The two main authors of old English prose were Aelfric and Wulfstan. Homilies, biographies of saints, sermons, and Bible translations are among the genre's elements. Aelfric, the Abbot of Eynsham, also authored numerous other homilies, pastoral letters, and translations in addition to three cycles of forty homilies in two catholic books.^[1]

The homilies and civil and church-related legal codes were written by York's archbishop, Wulfstan. Poetry had already given birth when drama first appeared in English literature; prose had already emerged. The first examples of theater are small pieces from monasteries that were performed in churches to convey biblical tales. They then evolved into plays with extended runtime. Dramas mostly drew inspiration from catholic customs and festivities where everyone from the king to the lowest citizens participated. After the Middle Ages of English Literature (C-100 to C-1500), English became the literary and spoken language of England. In late middle age. The author of Utopia, Thomas More (1478–1535), served as the focal point of the entire ideological realm. Between the years 500 and 1100 AD, known as the Old English Period, English literature only existed orally. Humanism began to flourish in England in the sixteenth century. Similar to Italy, England experienced the rise of humanism at a time when the needs of the ruling class the monarch, members of the council church, officials, and public servants were best served by the education that humanism championed.^[2]

In this century, being proficient in Latin writing became required. Humanists focused on grammar and the gracefully subdued syntax of the Ciceronian style to make it easier to manage domestic and diplomatic affairs of the state. During the

¹ Rees, R.J. (1973), English Literature: An introduction for Foreign Readers. Basinstoke and London: Macmillan Education Ltd.

² Moody, H. (1972), The study Literature. London George Allen and Unwin.

century that produced some of the best literature, humanist programs were also started. The Renaissance, which was characterized by intellectual and social activity, is where humanism has its roots. Italy was where humanism and its concepts initially emerged, followed by all of Europe. The discovery and evolution of the Greek and Roman classical civilizations' intellectual and social features are what can be referred to as humanism. In many ways, it is also a criticism of scholasticism, the preeminent school of thought during the medieval years. Scholasticism had been a dynamic lively approach in the early 12th and 13th centuries, but by the 14th century, minor aspects of philosophy and theology had become more ordered. Later, like the dancing angels on a pinhead, scholasticism was contested and discussed. The Greek satirist was immensely liked by the two companions, Desiderius Erasmus and Thomas More, who share a foundational regard for the right Christian ethics of a perfect society. Literature ceases to be literature if it departs from a humanistic perspective.

Hence Literature should be a deeply personal and social experience that reveals something about humans and human-related topics through its words, sentences, characters, stories, and motifs. To build a nation on a solid foundation, each generation needs to be aware of the ancient culture, traditions, and history from which men descended. This can only be done through literature, which can easily convey complicated ideas that are difficult to understand and require an infinite number of words to explain. Literature preserves the records created by famous authors, philosophers, poets, and other thinkers throughout the ages, documenting and interpreting what has occurred in the past and what is likely to occur in the future. Words can enrich culture and create an environment where a person will eventually love others as his brothers without regard to their caste, creed, religion, or nationality.^[3]

Conclusion. The very essence of humanism is to encourage people to use language and writing in ways that advance social well-being. Human life is so intertwined with literature and humanism that the absence of either of them causes uncontrollable, noisy, and unsatisfactory chaos. Aura of cooperation that attracts people together to live, work, and understand one another is prepared by good literature. Literature can benefit society in a variety of ways, including print, visual, aural, and oral oratory. Written exams may take the shape of

³ J.N. Mundra & S.C. Mundra (1994), A History of English Literature : Vol.-I. Bareilly, Prakash Book Depot.

fiction, nonfiction, poetry, prose, novels, short stories, or plays that adhere to specific historical eras and aesthetic standards in literature.

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